

SCIENTIFIC AND THEORETICAL STUDY OF THE FORMATION OF IDEAS ABOUT A HEALTHY LIFESTYLE

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Abstract. *The study of social concepts is a pressing issue, as their dynamics and transformations allow us to understand cultural changes. Social concepts, in turn, are formed through communication between members of a given group. The theory of social representations and the model of social knowledge develop their structure, manifestation, and dissemination in communicative and interactive processes, and also describe the functions of knowledge and experience in social practice. While psychology studies the formation of healthy lifestyle concepts among the population from the perspective of human character, behavior, and various psychological states, sociology primarily examines which aspects of our psyche, which seem mysterious to each of us, are associated with our feeling healthy, safe, and vigorous, and what opportunities we have to maintain our wealth—our health. This article analyzes the scientific and theoretical foundations of the concept of a healthy lifestyle, as well as the socio-psychological characteristics of this concept. The article also examines views on religious and social issues related to a healthy lifestyle and their implications.*

Key words: *healthy lifestyle, perceptions, socio-psychological characteristics, social perceptions, communicative, interactive, collective perceptions, structure of social perception.*

НАУЧНО-ТЕОРЕТИЧЕСКОЕ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЕ ФОРМИРОВАНИЯ ПРЕДСТАВЛЕНИЙ О ЗДОРОВОМ ОБРАЗЕ ЖИЗНИ

Аннотация. *Изучение социальных концепций является актуальной задачей, поскольку их динамика и трансформации позволяют нам понимать изменения в культуре. Социальные концепции, в свою очередь, формируются в процессе коммуникации между членами определенной группы. Теория социальных представлений и модель социального знания развивают их структуру, проявление и распространение в коммуникативных, интерактивных процессах, а также описывают функции знания и опыта в социальной практике. когда психология изучает формирование представлений о здоровом образе жизни среди населения с точки зрения человеческого характера, поведения и различных психологических состояний, социология в основном изучает, какие аспекты нашей психики, которые кажутся каждому из нас загадкой, связаны с тем, чтобы мы чувствовали себя здоровыми, невредимыми и бодрыми, какие у нас есть возможности для поддержания нашего богатства – нашего здоровья. В статье анализируются научно-теоретические основы концепции здорового образа жизни, социально-психологические особенности концепции здорового образа жизни. А также, в статье рассматриваются взгляды на религиозные и социальные проблемы здорового образа жизни и представления о них.*

Ключевые слова: *здоровый образ жизни, восприятия, социально-психологические характеристики, социальные восприятия, коммуникативные, интерактивные, коллективные восприятия, структура социального восприятия.*

SOG'LOM TURMUSH TARZI HAQIDA TASAVVURLARNI SHAKLLANTIRISHNI ILMIY VA NAZARIY O'RGANISH

Annotatsiya. Ijtimoiy tushunchalarni o'rganish dolzarb vazifadir, chunki ularning dinamikasi va o'zgarishlari bizga madaniy o'zgarishlarni tushunishga imkon beradi. O'z navbatida, ijtimoiy tushunchalar ma'lum bir guruh a'zolari o'rtasidagi muloqot orqali shakllanadi. Ijtimoiy tasavvurlar nazariyasi va ijtimoiy bilim modeli ularning tuzilishini, namoyon bo'lishini va kommunikativ va interaktiv jarayonlarda tarqalishini rivojlantiradi, shuningdek, ijtimoiy amaliyotda bilim va tajribaning funktsiyalarini tavsiflaydi. Psixologiya aholi orasida sog'lom turmush tarzi tushunchalarining shakllanishini inson xarakteri, xulq-atvori va turli psixologik holatlar nuqtai nazaridan o'rganganda, sotsiologiya birinchi navbatda har birimiz uchun sirli tuyuladigan ruhiyatimizning qaysi jihatlari bizning soglig'imiz, farovonligimiz va hayotiyligimiz bilan bog'liqligini va boyligimiz – sog'lig'imizni saqlash uchun qanday imkoniyatlarga ega ekanligimizni o'rganadi. Ushbu maqolada sog'lom turmush tarzi tushunchasining ilmiy va nazariy asoslari, shuningdek, uning ijtimoiy-psixologik xususiyatlari tahlil qilinadi. Maqolada shuningdek, sog'lom turmush tarzi bilan bog'liq diniy va sotsial masalalar va ular haqidagi g'oyalar haqida fikrlar o'rganiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: sog'lom turmush tarzi, idrok, ijtimoiy-psixologik xususiyatlar, ijtimoiy idrok, kommunikativ, interaktiv, jamoaviy idrok, ijtimoiy.

KIRISH

The state public health protection system is a complex of legislative, organizational, and financial measures aimed at fostering a healthy lifestyle and preventing socially significant diseases.

This area is regulated through the adoption of legal acts, the development of national health promotion programs, the creation of appropriate infrastructure, and the coordination of the activities of medical, educational, and social institutions.

The legislative framework establishes legal norms for protecting citizens' health, defines mechanisms for limiting the spread of harmful habits, and regulates requirements for food quality and working conditions. Anti-tobacco legislation restricts smoking areas and tobacco advertising, while legal regulation of alcohol sales is aimed at reducing the availability of alcoholic beverages to the population. Sanitary and hygienic standards establish environmental safety and drinking water quality standards.

The implementation of state programs involves the development of preventive medicine, the creation of sports infrastructure, the organization of mass physical education and health events, and the subsidization of health-promoting projects. Creating an accessible environment for physical education includes the construction of sports facilities, the development of recreational areas in urban areas, and providing the population with opportunities for active leisure. Funding for preventive medical examinations, screenings, and vaccinations facilitates early detection of diseases and reduces the burden of chronic conditions.

Interdepartmental collaboration between healthcare, education, culture, and social welfare agencies ensures a synergistic effect in the implementation of public health promotion policies. Coordinating the efforts of various agencies allows for reaching all age and social groups of the population, adapting prevention programs to the specific needs of target audiences, and creating a sustainable system for motivating citizens to lead a healthy lifestyle.

To understand the concepts of a healthy lifestyle, it is necessary to turn to the ideas and views of the psychology of concepts.

Accordingly, below we will try to briefly discuss the socio-psychological characteristics of the concepts. The study of social concepts is an urgent task, since their dynamics and transformations allow us to understand changes in culture. Social concepts, in turn, are formed in the process of communication between members of a certain group.

According to the theory of social representations, the object of representations is a sociocognitive “distorted” object, which is the subject of discourses at various levels (interpersonal, media, cultural). Accordingly, while interactionism, which analyzes social representations in the form of a symbol, gravitates more towards sociology, the theory of social representations can claim a psychological status related to a number of social phenomena: ideas, collective representations and memories, sociocultural construction of the individual and collective “I”.

MAIN PART

The theory of social representations and the model of social knowledge develop their structure, manifestation and dissemination in communicative, interactive processes, and also describe the functions of knowledge and experience in social practice.

The concept of social imagination was first introduced into science by Serge Moskvisi in the 1960s in his work to popularize psychoanalytic ideas among the French population and began to be widely used. Initially, this direction was aimed at studying the social manifestations of scientific knowledge. However, later, the explanatory scope of this theory expanded, and now it is perceived as a field studying the doctrine of social experience, its structure, as well as the full dynamics and role in social practice. Historically, this theory originates from the distinction between social and collective imagination in the sociology of Emil Durkheim [1]. He was one of the first to draw attention to the important role of collective imagination in the structure of our language, traditions and institutions, and to the extent to which these sets of imaginations are further embodied in individual thinking by social thinking.

Since the 1960s, social imagination theory has been the leading paradigm in France, Italy, Spain, Portugal, and Latin America. In the mid-1980s, interest in this area arose in the British Isles, and later in France, the USA, Canada and Australia, and academic discussions on this issue intensified.

Sharing the structure of the social imagination, researchers J. K. Abrick identified a core that provides stability to the group imagination, and an ever-changing peripheral part that leads to the adaptation of the group to changes in the world. The structure of the imagination depends on changes in attitude, the core remains stable, and the peripheral part changes [2].

If we look at the development of modern views on healthy living, historical information dates back to 1832, when the American physician Sylvester Graham (1794-1851) preached vegetarianism to Christians who immigrated from England to America through his strong Christian faith. This was due to the fact that some Christian traditions considered it a sin to eat animal meat, including eggs. Plague was widespread in the U.S. state of Philadelphia at the time, and many people were dying from the disease. Graham observed that none of those who followed his advice on vegetarianism suffered from plague. Then he decided that a vegetarian diet would increase the body's defenses, and continued to widely promote and spread this idea [3].

Thus, there is a growing number of people who take an unconventional approach to health issues, or rather, doctors, among whom there are both adherents and scientists who have done world-class work in the field of healthy lifestyles.

In America - Howard Hay, Jennings, Troll, Tilden, Jackson, Herbert Shelton, Paul Bragg, Alice Chase; in Japan, Kotsuzo Nishi, George Ozawa, Imamura Motoo; in Germany, Max Gerzon; in Israel - Mikhail Goren; in Russia - Yuri Nikolaev, Alexander Mikulin, A.N. Kokosov, Nadezhda Semenova and others.

It should also be noted that many of those who switched to a healthy lifestyle themselves suffered from serious diseases, some of which were recognized as incurable by official medicine.

However, they did not kneel before the disease, but fought for their lives. For example, Howard Hay - kidney disease, Paul Bragg - pulmonary tuberculosis, Kotsuzo Nishi - intestinal tuberculosis, Max Gerzon - migraine, Michael Goren - kidney tuberculosis, Alexander Mikulin - heart attack, Nadezhda Semenova - polyarthritis, Louise Hay - uterine cancer, and they recovered from serious diseases only by improving their lifestyle.

The most prominent representatives of official medicine, academicians Yuri Lisitsyn, Nikolai Amosov, Fedr Uglov, Evgeny Chazov, G.I. Saregorodtsev, Galina Shatalova and many other scientists who applied their proposals in their lives, supported the ideas and views of these adherents of a healthy lifestyle. Academician Yu. Lisitsyn, summarizing many years of scientific research and existing ideas and opinions in this area, concludes that human health is 50-55% dependent on lifestyle, 20-25% on hereditary factors, 15-20% on the environment, and medical care can provide only 8-10% of human health [4].

The first ideas about a healthy lifestyle in our country go back to the Avesta, the holy book of Zoroastrianism. The main idea of the Zoroastrian religion - "good deed, good word and good thought" - is still an important spiritual basis for personal development and the formation of a healthy lifestyle.

Zoroastrian rituals combine moral and physical education, and seek to bring to life such healthy ideas as kindness, creativity and mercy. Noble ideas are celebrated in society, people with qualities such as kindness, patriotism and enlightenment are highly respected, and other vices that bring shame, such as theft, robbery and envy of other people's property, are condemned.

We see that the ideas of a healthy lifestyle in later periods were enriched by the ideas of Islam. Ideals of virtue in Islam do not put worldly and religious affairs above each other. This promotes a healthy environment. The meaning of the phrase "Dil ba yoru dast ba kor" is associated with the name of Bohovuddin Naqshband: "May your heart be in Allah, and your hands in labor", which encourages a person to be a believer and earn a living by his own work.

Such noble ideals have not lost their value to this day.

Scientific experiments show that philosophers, ethnographers, historians, sociologists, psychologists and educators have conducted a number of scientific studies on the philosophical aspects of the problem of a healthy lifestyle, the role of a healthy lifestyle in social relations, its educational impact on society and the formation of ideas about a healthy lifestyle among the population, especially among young people. In their view, a way of life is a daily life determined by historical socio-economic and spiritual factors, and consists of relationships, traditions and customs formed on this basis.

The research of Western scientists R.Bunton, S.Hermann, G.MacDonald and A.Scrivener in the last decade has been aimed at promoting the psychology of human health protection,

ensuring that its promotion is based on theoretical and practical conclusions and knowledge, as well as the development of the existing health care system.

The issues of raising young people based on a healthy lifestyle and the formation of their ideas about a healthy lifestyle are scientifically and psychologically substantiated by the works of scientists from the countries of the Commonwealth of Independent States, including A.F.Georgievsky, P.L.Dribinsky, A.D.Dubachaya, T.V.Kamenskaya, A.D.K.Arabasheva, E.A.Mensha, G.P.Novikova, E.A.Pipko, G.M.Populo, O.A.Laskina and others.

Some Russian scientists, for example, T.F. Akbashev, B.A. Classes, supplement the spiritual health of a person with a combination of three factors: social, intellectual and reproductive health.

In their opinion, intellectual health is reflected in thinking, perception and transmission of information, and social health is expressed in a person's social activity, search for his place in society and professional development. Reproductive health manifests itself in relationships with parents, family relationships, sexual culture, birth and parenting.

R.Iseman, one of the researchers working on the issue of health and healthy living, also highlights the following levels:

Physical, i.e. genetic, biochemical, metabolic, morphological, functional; spiritual, i.e. missionary, mental, personal; socio-spiritual or moral [5].

Cognitive, behavioral and emotional components of a person's attitude to health, according to G.S.Nikiforov, can be considered as a personal quality, consisting of the desire to maintain health, or vice versa. Many people have serious contradictions hidden in the health care issue. Even without turning to scientific data, the idea of health as a value is quite high in our minds. However, in relation to health care (healthy lifestyle), the severity of the affective, behavioral component does not correspond at all to the amount of knowledge about health or the strength of emotional reactions to its weakening. The activities of most people aimed at maintaining and promoting health do not correspond to the intensity of emotional attitude. This is true not only for healthy people, but also for those who already have serious diseases [5].

Sociological, spiritual and psychological criteria for a healthy lifestyle can be described as follows:

paying special attention to the clothing of young girls and women in the family, educational institutions and public places;

widespread dissemination of the unique traditions and values of our people in relation to a healthy lifestyle, the teachings of fathers and mothers, as well as the experience of healthy spiritual families as an exemplary factor in the formation of a culture of behavior among young people in the family and public places;

the use of events and traditions of family sports held in our country to form a positive attitude of young people to sports, including family sports;

formation among family members, primarily among young people, of a culture of understanding the essence of life, respect for the value of life and rational organization of life;

the formation of social thinking about the value of water, air, land and water resources by spreading among the masses the principles of moderation and purity in Islamic philosophy.

In general, the formation of the philosophy of health is directly related to healthy and folk rituals, customs and national eternal values.

Existing social conditions to a certain extent have a significant impact on the lifestyle of people. In everyday life, their moral and aesthetic views, behavior, actions and life ideas are absorbed into their inner world, beliefs and become a way of life and way of thinking.

The most important social aspect of the lifestyle is the social work of members of society, their relationships, family and activities in everyday life, how the physical and spiritual abilities of people are manifested in the natural and social environment. In addition, the formation of a healthy lifestyle in the family plays an important role in educating members of our society, especially young people, in adherence to the ideas of national patriotism, humanism, as well as national and universal values.

Sources note that the concept of a healthy lifestyle is a lifestyle aimed at organizing everyday life based on certain laws, maintaining and promoting health, and that this lifestyle should represent how and in what form a person organizes his life, and for this each person needs to have an idea of a healthy lifestyle, spirituality and worldview [6]. At the same time, an important component is the attitude of a person to his own health. We can say that this problem arises because of the fact that society begins to realize its inability to solve health problems on its own. Based on this, it can be noted that "risk factors" are associated with illness and death, which means that their study and assessment are relevant for both sociology and medicine [7].

CONCLUSION

In this sense, when sociology studies the formation of ideas about a healthy lifestyle among the population in terms of human character, behavior and various states: she mainly studies what aspects of our psyche that seem like a mystery to each of us, related to making us feel healthy, unharmed and alert, what opportunities we have to maintain our wealth - our health - by managing it, and the formation of ideas about a healthy lifestyle is increasingly entering our lives as science and useful practice, studying how each of us can manage our own mental state, mitigate it through timely monitoring of changes taking place in our minds and ways to adapt to changing conditions as well as prevention.

From the above, it can be concluded that there are many concepts, theories, directions, views, approaches, various aspects and directions in various scientific fields regarding the formation of ideas about a healthy lifestyle in young people. However, it should not be forgotten that for the formation of ideas about a healthy lifestyle, the understanding and perception of these ideas by the person himself, his social and psychological characteristics are also of great importance.

The study allows us to formulate conclusions regarding the theoretical and practical aspects of promoting a healthy lifestyle in modern society. An analysis of the medical and biological foundations of health confirms the need for a comprehensive approach to strengthening the body's functional reserves through optimizing physical activity, rationalizing nutrition, and preventing destructive behavioral patterns.

The importance of psychological well-being as an integral component of a healthy lifestyle, ensuring the individual's adaptive resilience to stress, is revealed. An examination of social mechanisms for promoting health-promoting behavior demonstrates the role of public policy and educational programs in fostering a culture of responsible health care.

The study's results highlight the need to further improve preventive measures, expand informational and educational efforts, and create motivational conditions for various social groups to implement healthy lifestyle principles.

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